

Development of Unit-Based Dashboards for Communicating Nursing Quality of Care Data

Ronald Norby, DNP, RN, NEA-BC, Jill Berg PhD, RN, and Margaret Brady, PhD, RN, CPNP--CP

Hospital-Acquired Iatrogenic Events

- 70% of US hospital accidents due to falls
- Other iatrogenic events:
 - Hospital-acquired pressure injuries
 - Catheter/central line infections
 - Omitting needed care
 - Poor patient satisfaction
- Iatrogenic events are largely preventable
- Essential to create “culture of quality” where nurses engage in:
 - Data collection & analysis
 - Designing remedial interventions
 - Assessing impact of interventions

Key Findings from Literature

Successful quality improvement requires:

- Systematic & systemic approach
- Evidence-based interventions
- Ongoing front-line staff engagement
- Meaningful and on-going feedback

When nurses get feedback on their care, evidence-based protocols have been developed for:

- Screening patients at risk
- Monitoring vulnerable patients
- Implementing interventions

Research/QI projects increase
Successful innovations are disseminated

Theoretical Framework

IHI Model for Improvement

Institute for Healthcare Improvement, 2018

Problem Statement, Project and Setting

- **Problem**—Timely & informative communication of quality of care data not consistently provided to staff nurses
- **Purpose**—Improve communication pathways related to feedback on nursing-specific quality of care indicators throughout the Department of Nursing
- **Project**—Design & test implementation of unit-based dashboards to provide feedback on quality of care

Unit-Based Dashboard

Rancho Los Amigos Nursing

Quality ~ Safety ~ Outcomes

Pressure Injury Surveillance

Unit A

November 2017 Dashboard

Most Patients on Unit are at Risk For Developing Pressure Injuries

Unit A Compliance with SKIN Bundle

Unit-Based Action Items

1. Review/Discuss SKIN Bundle Components Where Lower Compliance Exists
2. Design Intervention Strategies for Low-Performing Components
3. Implement Strategies
4. Conduct Daily Pressure Injury Huddles

Dashboard Implementation

- Aids in “cultural transformation” to evidence-based practice
- Must assess and address level of staff competence in data interpretation
- Should be geared to uniqueness of each nursing unit
- Must be accompanied with staff education
- Need to include options for a “call to action”
- Frequently leads to identifying the need for systems re-design
- Should be accompanied by staff engagement in designing improvement interventions
- Assessment of intervention effectiveness needs to become a part of the daily routine

The Setting

Rancho Los Amigos

- Nationally prominent rehabilitation center
- 395-beds – 9 inpatient units
- Acute care & rehabilitation
- Routinely collects quality of care data
- Two-25 bed pilot units selected for project
- Approximately 35 RNs on each unit with 50/50 split of ADN and BSN

Methods of Evaluation

- 5-Item pre-post project questionnaire
- Unit observations by PI
- Perceptions of dashboard usefulness by:
 - Nurse executives
 - Leadership staff
 - Councils/collaboratives

Results

- No major difference in RN pre/post surveys

- Unit observations revealed that dashboards:
 - Posted but sometimes obscured
- Discussions were held:
 - Somewhat superficial
 - Absence of front-line RN involvement
- Perceptions of dashboards
 - Unanimous opinion of importance
 - Effective tool for data dissemination